

DECORATING SILVER NANOPARTICLES ONTO MULTIWALL CARBON NANOTUBE SHEETS

WM Zhao^a, M. Li^b, H-X Peng^{a*}

^a Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol, BS8 1TR, UK

^b School of Chemistry, University of Bristol, BS8 1TS, UK

*H.X.Peng@bristol.ac.uk

SUMMARY

Silver nanoparticles were synthesized by using acid-treated multiwalled carbon nanotubes by photochemical reduction method. MWNTs sheet was fabricated by a paper-making process. Compared to pristine MWNT sheet, the electrical conductivity of the nanohybrid sheets increased from 27.7 S/cm to 40.0 S/cm, which is also related to increased electromagnetic shielding effectiveness.

Key words: Carbon nanotubes, Nanoparticles, Decoration, Photochemical, Conductivity

INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotube sheets have great potential for specific engineering applications owing to their unique, tunable properties such as conductivity. To date, most CNT sheet materials (e.g., buckypapers) are fabricated by using single wall carbon nanotubes (SWNTs). However, multi-wall carbon nanotubes (MWNTs) are much cheaper than SWNTs, and better suited to large scale industrial applications. One drawback of MWCNTs is that the conductivity of MWNTs is typically one or two orders lower than that of SWNTs. The simplest way to achieve low-resistance ohmic contacts to these structures is to coat metals onto the nanotube surface. The only approach so far then is to deposit metals through a chemical reaction on the inner or outer surfaces of the tubes. [1] There are many ingenious methods of depositing metal nanoparticles onto CNT substrates in the literature, each offering varying degrees of control of particle size and distribution along the CNT. [2] However, the metals in these cases were formed by post-reduction of metal compounds with no specificity to the nanotube surface. Alternatively, there is a general method in which the nanotube surface can be modified by oxidation in order to obtain a more controlled and specific nucleation of metals and metal compounds on the surface. Oxidized nanotubes were normally covered by carboxylic (-COOH), carbonyl (-C=O) and hydroxyl (-OH) groups, which all increase the chemical reactivity and specificity of the relatively inert carbon surface.

In this study, the MWNTs were treated in a mixture acid of H₂SO₄/HNO₃ (3:1) to functionalize the surface with acid sites. Highly conductive silver nanoparticles were then homogeneously decorated onto MWNT walls by in-situ photochemical reduction of silver

nitrate onto carbon nanotubes in the presence of Triton X-100 (TX-100) surfactant. The nanotube sheets were fabricated by vacuum infiltrating processing. The effect of silver nanoparticles on the electrical properties was investigated by comparing the pristine nanotube sheet with the decorated nanotube sheets.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The MWNTs (Sigma Aldrich) were produced by Chemical Vapour Deposition (CVD) method, with a purity of > 99%, up to 20 μ m in length and their diameters around 12nm. Pristine MWNTs (4.32 g) were added to 120ml a mixture acid of H₂SO₄/HNO₃ (3:1). The mixture was placed in an ultrasonic bath (40 kHz) for 30 min and then stirred for 4 h under 100^oC. The mixture was then diluted with distilled water, no sediment was found after a whole night. The resulting solution was then vacuum-filtered through a 0.22 μ m Millipore alumina membrane and subsequently washed with distilled water until the pH of the filtrate was ca. 7. The filtered solid was dried under vacuum for 24 h at 40 ^oC, yielding MWNT-COOH (2.5879 g). 100mg of acid-treated MWNTs were dispersed in distilled water in the presence of TX-100 surfactant, and a 250ml silver nitrate solution (0.2wt%) was then added into the MWNTs suspension and stirred under UV light with a wave length of 365nm at 60-^oC. The sheets was fabricated by filtering the resulted mixture through Millipore filter and subsequently washed with distilled water and ethanol.

Zeta Potential Analyzer was used to measure the Zeta potential and mobility of the resulted acid treated MWNTs. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to characterize the morphologies of the as-synthesized MWNTs. The SEM is JEOL 1530 equipped with a thermally assisted filed emission gun operating at 10 keV. The morphologies of nanoparticles stabilized by MWNTs were observed by using transmission electron microscopy (TEM, JEOL 1200). To prepare the TEM samples, a tiny drop of well dispersed samples was placed onto the carbon coated TEM copper grid. A fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscope was used to study the acid treated MWNTs. The acid-treated MWNTs were mixed with dried KBr powder and pressed to form the semi-transparent pellets. Electrical conductivity measurements were conducted using the four-probe method (A 4284A Precision LCR meter) at room temperature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1a shows the optical image of acid treated MWNTs in aqueous solutions after two months. The oxidized nanotubes disperse better in solution with a mean Zeta potential of $-34.03mV$ and a mean mobility of $-2.66(\mu/s)/(V/cm)$. The better dispersed nanotubes together with the carboxyl functional groups yield a higher concentration of crosslinking, resulting in a higher bending modulus [3]. Fig.1b shows a free standing nanotube sheet, with a diameter of 40mm and a thickness of 100 μ m, were stiff enough to show a metal shining surface. Also the resulted nanotube sheets were more flexible and much stronger than the pristine nanotube sheets, which were very brittle and could not be bended.

Fig. 1 a) Optical image of acid-treat MWNTs in aqueous solutions (left: dilute; right: concentrated); b) the nanotube sheet prepared by vacuum filtrating processing

Fig. 2 FTIR spectrum of the acid-treated MWNTs

Fig.2 shows the IR spectra of the acid-treated MWNTs. The dominant peak at 1613 cm^{-1} can be assigned to characteristic of acid carbonyl (C=O) stretches, and the broad band at 3400 cm^{-1} is identified as O-H stretching mode in carboxylic acid groups. The peak at 1587 cm^{-1} is attributed to the vibration of carbon skeleton of the carbon nanotubes. The results indicate that carboxylic acid groups have been attached to the surface of CNT.

Fig.3 shows the TEM image of silver nanoparticles which were synthesized by using acid MWNTs as stabilizing agents without TX-100 surfactant. With the nanotubes as backbone, the nanoparticles were lined up to form a stable assembly, which indicated that there were active sites on the acid-treated MWNTs walls which aided the nucleation and growth of silver nanoparticles on the surface. However, the particles or agglomerations had quite a large size distribution, from 10 to 100nm, with shapes of hexagon, pentagon, and sphere. Also the nanoparticles can only anchor on certain nanotubes, indicating an inhomogenous distribution of the nanoparticles on the future nanotube/NPs sheet.

Fig.3 a) TEM image showing pristine MWNTs; b) silver nanoparticles synthesized by acid treated MWNTs; c) silver nanoparticles synthesized by using TX100 and acid treated MWNTs; d) the X-ray energy dispersion spectra of nano hybrid sample.

In another experiment, silver nanoparticles were synthesized by using acid-treated MWNTs in the presence of TX-100, and the silver nanoparticles were stabilized on the nanotubes' wall and well dispersed as well. This indicated that the TX-100 is necessary in controlling the nanoparticle size, distribution and preventing from agglomeration. Although the TEM

samples were prepared by dispersing the resulting nanohybrids in water by strong ultrasonicator, the nanotubes were still tightly connected by the nanoparticles and a conductive path thus being set up, which enhanced the transport properties of the future nanotube sheets, Fig. 3c. The X-ray energy dispersion spectra of nanohybrid sample confirms the presence of silver atoms on the oxidized nanotubes (peaks other than those corresponding to Ag are due to the support grid), Fig.3d.

Fig. 4 Schematic view of the process for anchoring silver nanoparticles onto MWNT nanotubes.

From above analysis, it is evident that the acid-treated MWNTs were considerably effective in stabilizing silver nanoparticles. The stabilizing mechanism was proposed as the following: the oxygen elements on the acid-treated MWNTs walls provided the nucleation centers for metal ion and then stabilized the nanoparticles after they were formed. The nanotubes act as the template on which the as-formed nanoparticles can line up to form a stable assembly due to their special structures, Fig. 4, [4].

Fig.4 a) Optical image of fabricated MWNT sample; b) the SEM micrographs of the surface; and c) the side view of nanotube sheets

A closer SEM examination (Fig. 4b) revealed that the nanotube sheets is in fact rather rough, and the tubes form a random, heavily interconnected macroporous system. Their dominant orientation is normal to the direction of the filtration, without any bundling. By quantitative SEM image analysis results, the apparent pore diameter is 30-50nm. R.Smajda et al.[5] found that the apparent pore diameter of the MWNT sheets as largely independent of the solvent type, nanotube amount and sonication time used when preparing the samples. In the side view (Fig.4c) it is visible that the samples have a layered structure and the individual layer stretched tens of microns horizontally in the sheet and are separated by interlayer nanotube assemblies which appear to be less tightly bound.

The electrical resistance of CNT sheet is derived from two components: the resistance of the individual CNTs and the contact resistance between CNTs. The decorated Ag nanoparticles appear to further increase the carrier density, leading to an increase in conductivity, as shown in Table 1 [6]. Based on the theory of EMI shielding, the shielding effectiveness (SE) is described as

$$SE = 20 \log \left| (1/4n) [(1+n)^2 \exp(-ikd) - (1-n)^2 \exp(ikd)] \right| \quad (1)$$

Where the complex index of refraction n is related with the complex wave vector k ($= n\omega/c$). In good conductor approximation, the SE of monolayer films described in Eq. (1) is given as follows [7]:

$$SE_{mono} = 10 \log \left\{ \frac{1}{4} \left[\frac{\sigma}{2\omega\epsilon_0} \left(\cosh \frac{2d}{\delta} - \cosh \frac{2d}{\delta} \right) + 2 \sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{2\omega\epsilon_0}} \left(\sinh \frac{2d}{\delta} + \sinh \frac{2d}{\delta} \right) + 2 \left(\cosh \frac{2d}{\delta} + \cosh \frac{2d}{\delta} \right) \right] \right\} \quad (2)$$

where $\delta = \sqrt{2/\mu_0\omega\sigma}$ is the skin depth. For an electrically tin shield ($d \ll \delta$), Eq. (2) reduces to:

$$\begin{aligned}
 SE &\approx 20 \log\left(1 + \frac{Z_0 \sigma d}{2}\right) \\
 &= 20 \log(\sigma d) + 20 \log\left(\frac{1}{\sigma d} + \frac{Z_0}{2}\right)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3}$$

Where Z_0 ($=376.7\Omega$) is the wave impedance of free space. The result shows that the EMI SE increases as the σd increases, which means conductivity is an intrinsic parameter of the SE, and the thickness is an extrinsic parameter for the SE. As the thickness of the material increases, the SE becomes larger due to the increase of the absorption of the EM wave [8].

Table 1 Effect of silver nanoparticles on the conductivity and EMI SE of nanotube sheets.

Materials (monolayer)	σ (S/cm) (300K)	Thickness (d) /(μm)	SE (dB)
MWNT/ NPs	40	110	38.47254711
MWNT	27.7	120	36.06563174

CONCLUSION

Silver nanoparticles were synthesized by using photochemical reduction method and were used to decorate acid-treated multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). MWNTs sheet was fabricated by a paper-making process. FTIR showed that there were C–OH and C–O–C functional groups on the acid-treated MWNT walls. The carboxyl groups helped nanotubes well dispersed in aqueous and also yielded more crosslinking opportunities, which contributed to a stronger and higher bending modulus nanotube sheet. These acid-treated MWNTs can be used as excellent stabilizing substrates for silver nanoparticle synthesis. The silver nanoparticles synthesized on acid-treated MWNTs substrates in the presence of TX-100 were well dispersed and connected the nanotubes, which contributed to a higher electrical conductivity and electromagnetic shielding effective at the same time. The higher electrical and stronger mechanical properties enlarged the potential of macroscopic assemblies of nanotubes for various application fields.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank Mr Jones of School of Chemistry for help with TEM imaging. WM Zhao acknowledges the support from Overseas Research Scholarship Award Scheme and the University of Bristol Postgraduate Scholarship.

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